

Capacity
Building for
Accessible
Heritage

Annex Audio Guide Survey

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Abstract

An audio guide provides a recorded spoken commentary, normally through a handheld device, to a visitor attraction such as a museum. This survey records the most interesting comparative articles and products. The benefits and drawbacks of current solutions are described. Applications work with smartphones, tablets, wearable cameras, smart glasses and special production equipment. Cost and battery life are crucial factors. Smartphones and tablets have three key elements: impressive computational power, connectivity, and imaging capabilities. However, providing Augmented reality (AR) that meets a user's expectations requires power that is not available in current mobile devices technology.

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Introduction

Audio guide tours are based on points of interest, like key exhibits. For each point an audio track is available. To access and playback audio tracks, the numbers are physically situated close to the exhibits. The drawback of such solutions is physical intervention is needed in the exhibition space (number labels), and that the visitor has to carry a device in his/her hands or around the neck. Ongoing user interaction with the device is necessary which may disrupt the visit and distract from the museum experience¹.

Museum guide applications have been designed for mobile phones and smart glasses^{2,3,4,5}. In the case of mobile phones, visitors need to explicitly run the application, focus on the painting with the phone camera, and then check the information. Since these actions involve more effort than simply pressing a number on a traditional keypad, visitors tend to prefer the traditional option (this is similar to what occurs with the QR code approach). If the mobile phone is carried around the neck to alleviate the discomfort, problems with the perspective arise. For example, if the user turns the head to the side, the camera of such devices continues to capture the frontal image instead of capturing the image from the scene that the user is observing. Smart glasses have been also considered, however, they present issues for users that already wear prescription glasses; furthermore, smart glasses often suffer from overheating.

Interestingly, mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets are the closest current example of versatile mobile vision systems. Driven by consumer demand, these devices currently have three key elements: Impressive computational power, connectivity, and imaging capabilities. Not surprisingly, the computer vision community has found a highly versatile platform in smartphones and tablets. Pre-existing CV and augmented reality libraries and applications are being ported to such devices

¹ Wacker, Kreutz, Heller, Borchers (2016), *Maps and Location: Acceptance of Modern Interaction Techniques for Audio Guides*. In Proceedings of CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, pp. 1067–1071.

² Ruf, Kokiopoulou, Detyniecki, (2010). Mobile Museum Guide Based on Fast SIFT Recognition. In: Detyniecki, M., Leiner, U., Nürnberger, A. (eds) Adaptive Multimedia Retrieval. Identifying, Summarizing, and Recommending Image and Music. AMR 2008. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 5811. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-14758-6_14

³ Serubugo, Skantárová, Kjaersgard Nielsen, Kraus (2017), Comparison of Wearable Optical See-through and Handheld Devices as Platform for an Augmented Reality Museum Guide. In Proceedings of International Joint Conference on Computer Vision, Imaging and Computer Graphics Theory and Applications, (VISIGRAPP) pages 179-186. DOI:10.5220/0006093901790186

⁴ Altwaijry, Moghimi Belongie, (2014), Recognizing locations with Google Glass: A case study, IEEE Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision, pp. 167-174, doi:10.1109/WACV.2014.6836105.

⁵ Vallez, Krauss, Espinosa-Aranda, Pagani, Seirafi, Deniz, Automatic Museum Audio Guide. Sensors 2020, 20, 779. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20030779>

and, most importantly, novel applications are arising. Arguably, this is the closest computer vision has ever come to be in the hands of everyone. Advances in mobile devices' capabilities have overshadowed those of vision platforms developed in the context of WSN research. Despite the phenomenal success of mobile devices and their imaging capabilities, there are, however, some crucial factors: (a) Power and (b) unused sensors. To illustrate the problem with power, take for example one of the visual application fields of mobile devices: Augmented reality (AR). AR makes use of the highest-bandwidth input sensor, i.e., video cameras. Combined with computer vision algorithms, AR has the potential to provide content that alters our visual reality. However, the biggest problem with providing AR that meets a user's expectations is power. AR at 25–30 Hz that seamlessly integrates content from multiple sources requires power that is simply not available in current mobile devices. Besides, a single RGB camera with a few megapixels is no longer expected, as we soon will see hundreds of megapixels, embedded stereo pairs, HDR, embedded depth cameras, etc. All of these devices increase power requirements.

We recorded the most interesting comparative articles and products.

Generally:

- Equipment: other products have their equipment and others are provided as apps for smartphones
- Configuration: most provide online CMS platforms with a simple registration. Some people take care of everything after sending the material
- Cost: in some sites, it is mentioned in the form of monthly/annual subscription etc. According to an article "For a small museum, it reaches 10,000-12,000 euros". With FREE I marked the free ones

Products

Open / Free

izi.TRAVEL

<https://www.izi.travel/en>

An online tool, registration needed video guide. izi.TRAVEL is an open and free story-telling platform for producers to publish stories and a smartphone app for consumers to hear was born in 2011. The idea was to establish a platform to connect cities, museums and their stories with travellers, who wanted to explore the world in a brand new, innovative way: via a global, open and free platform.

SmartGuide

<https://www.smart-guide.org/>

SmartGuide is a ready-built platform for publishing your own engaging and certified Covid-safe guides. Create a digital guide yourself for free in SmartGuide CMS (Content Management System) in as little as 60 minutes.

ECHOES

<https://echoes.xyz/>

Empowering creatives with cutting-edge tools. End-to-end creative platform, enabling you to create, publish and discover geolocated audio walks. Digital tools for our community of makers, storytellers and explorers working with locative audio (sound triggered by a listener's physical movement). A sound (or multiple sounds) contained within shapes on the map, creates geofenced areas. These will trigger content when listeners physically walk inside, by using GPS to determine their location or their proximity using iBeacon technology. Layer sounds in subtle or rich ways, guide the audience, surprise and entertain. A completely different way to experience our physical environment, a threshold where the magic happens. Spatial audio brings sonic journeys alive with immersive surround sound audio over headphones, no specialist technology is required. Incredible 360° audio that sounds like you're there with ambisonic recordings.

TravelStorys App

<https://travelstorys.com/>

Exploring travel places. Free GPS Self-Guided Audio Tours - For Travelers and Virtual Travelers Build Tours to Reach New Audiences.

Proprietary with Freemium access model

Locatify

<https://locatify.com/automatic-museum-guide/>

Locatify Museum Guide is an Icelandic software development company originally founded to harness the latest mobile technology to share local stories with travellers. Founded in 2009 by Steinunn-Anna Gunnlaugsdottir and Leifur Bjornsson, Locatify's SmartGuide app utilised the introduction of mobile internet and GPS to deliver on-location stories in Iceland. A little ahead of its time, the SmartGuide app didn't take off, but it did spark the creation of what would later become known as the Creator CMS – which would quickly grow to include treasure hunt games and indoor experiences for museums. From humble beginnings in Iceland to claiming the world's first BLE Beacon (and UWB) enabled audio guides, recognition by WIRED, European Space Agency, RFID Journal and the Financial Times. Locatify has grown into a leading company and platform for enabling location-based storytelling and gamification apps and experiences.

Copernicus

<http://www.copernicus-guide.com/en/index-museum.html>

Copernicus is the innovative, self-learning, fully automatic media guide system, which you can easily create, modify and extend without deeper technical knowledge.

xamoom

<https://xamoom.com/about-us/>

xamoom Museum Guide develops maintains and hosts a content management system with supporting tools. To secure our technological leadership we constantly enrich the core product (cms, web clients, smart apps, SDKs, backend, and our service app) with easy to use and cutting-edge features that bring our customers to success. xamoom has its origin in a cultural net project (pingeb.org, Project Ingeborg Bachmann). After winning the Bank Austria Art prize, Bruno Hautzenberger and Georg Holzer founded xamoom to create more projects like this – with ease. In the meantime, it evolved into many different industries – from tourism to museums and mobile marketing.

Orpheo Touch

<https://orpheogroup.com/>

Orpheo Touch is a state of the art digital guide combining the performance of a high-end smartphone with the robustness of an audio guide. We have simplified mobile device management making device management easier than ever. New capabilities include augmented reality (AR), 360 Technology, geo-fencing/geo-positioning, indoor beacon positioning, video syncing and more. Designed and manufactured in Europe, the Orpheo Touch Multimedia guide was created to be handed out to visitors and for intensive use in on-site (indoor and outdoor) operation with a shock-resistant and water-resistant casing. The Touch blends all the latest technology features to enable the visitor to experience attributes of an application that are NOT AVAILABLE or executable with many Android phones. We can build the app for you or we can integrate your existing app in the Touch, also consider using air set headphones for a full experience. The product is also compatible with Orpheo D-box, made to optimize onsite distribution and collect tour data. The Orpheo Touch is a multimedia guide combining performance and robustness. A true concentrate of technologies, this digital companion offers beautiful image quality, a wireless charging connector and a shock-resistant case. It comes with a tour app generator, MyOrpheo Studio.

Nubart

<https://www.nubart.eu/>

The audio guide Visitors Keep Nubart® enables museums, monuments, showrooms and other visitable venues to offer hygienic multimedia guides without the need for dedicated devices or expensive app development. An attractive branded card with a unique, non-transferable code is the visitor's gateway to a web app (PWA) with rich multimedia content. Visitors listen to the audio tour

directly on their smartphones (BYOD). Our innovative audio guides are accessible and profitable for the venue. Even for temporary exhibitions! Museums get great insight through visitor usage data and feedback.

Audio Tour Apps

<https://www.youraudiotour.com/>

Create professional audio tours that are available on any phone or computer. It can be easily shared and downloaded onto Android and iOS devices. Showcase your town's public art exhibits or an interesting neighbourhood. Towns and cities use Your Audio Tour to help teach locals and tourists about history and architecture. Create a modern tour that all your visitors can enjoy. Not only will visitors be able to use the tour onsite. Universities create audio tours to educate students and showcase their campuses. Your Audio Tour makes it easy for institutions to create unique and useful audio tours. a virtual tour of the museum online. QR Codes for each exhibit. Audio tours guide visitors through the site and teach history. Parks and trails build tours to teach visitors as they enjoy outdoor experiences. Visitors can purchase and listen to self-guided tours created by tourism providers. This provides an additional source of income and a way to promote attractions and local businesses.

My Tours

<https://www.mytoursapp.com/>

Transforms walks, museum tours and audio guides into apps, pricing Connecting People, Places & Stories. We provide world-class digital solutions for destinations with stories to share. Harnesses the power of technology to allow your visitors to engage deeper, explore further, and discover more.

Hearonymus

<https://www.mytoursapp.com/>

Hearonymus was founded in 2012 in Vienna. Its goal was to create a simple and affordable way for businesses in culture and tourism to gain all the benefits of audio guides on smartphones. With the possibility of having the entire content produced externally. The Hearonymus standard audio guide for smartphones was born. In many countries, visitors look forward to now enjoying the same look and feel of the guides in numerous places wherever they are. Another goal was to make the content of audio guides available to the general public outside of opening hours. Download a guide to your smartphone at home, listen, become curious, and go there. The idea of a platform for audio guides for smartphones has sparked great interest in the culture and tourism industries right from the start. The numbers from the foundation to the present day show that the concept is well received

Services and platforms

RSF

<https://rsf-museo.com/>

An ecosystem of solutions, designed and manufactured by RSF in France, to enrich and enhance museum visit routes. Discover the extent of our solutions RSF has a range of audio guides, multimedia guides and tour guides that combine simplicity, robustness and interactivity. Find the solution adapted to your scenography. RSF supports its clients with scenographic advice, assistance and technical support, after-sales service, audio guide rental and content management. RSF has a range of audioguides combining simplicity, robustness and interactivity. Museum operators and scenographers will find in the RSF audio guide that offers solutions adapted to any type of itinerary.

Clio Muse Tours

<https://cliomusetours.com/>

Clio Muse Tours was founded in 2014 to promote the world's cultural heritage by using modern technology tools. We have created over 450 self-guided tours in over 35 countries in collaboration with tour guides, museums and organizations. It puts people behind the company and our common passion to put together culture and travel experiences. Supports diversity, creativity and equality and we're proud of the work culture we've built. Creates products to stimulate the best experience for cultural heritage visitors through constant innovation while safeguarding inclusiveness, transparency, mindful fun, and respect for our team and customers

Audio tours

<http://www.audiotours.com/>

A one-stop-shop for audio tours and multimedia experiences, from initial concept to final recording – including apps.

Help to find ideas that may not have occurred to you before, and we will seek to establish the significance and purpose of your project, offer alternatives, discuss target groups and technology, and inform you about the projected timescale and costs – all in a friendly, relaxed brainstorming session or workshop. We know from experience what works where, and what does not. Thanks to our advice, you will be able to steer clear of all the pitfalls and use a targeted approach to implement your project.

Audio tours and multimedia experiences are not limited to a chronological list of historical events and places of interest. Copywriters are storytellers who do exhaustive research and link everything together. They use the full range of their considerable creative skills to immerse their audience completely in the experience. Professional translators who know and use only the correct words, phrases and idioms for their language. Sound production communicates more than what one can see for ourselves, so you can understand it far more quickly, remember it far more clearly and recount it far more easily than mere abstract explanations and descriptions. Depending on the script, we bring historical figures to life, including one or more narrators, and add music, sound effects and even aspects of the dramatic arts. This is because you will only have an authentic experience, and go home

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with a deeper understanding of what you have heard if you are drawn unexpectedly and irresistibly into the story.

tonwelt

<https://www.tonwelt.com/>

Guiding solutions is one of the leading suppliers of interactive visitor guidance systems in Europe. Supports museums, galleries, and exhibition centres as well as a wide range of tourist attractions and companies with innovative technology and individually designed solutions. As a full-service provider, combines creative content productions with reliable hardware and software solutions for sustainable and exciting knowledge transfer. Conveys information to your target group precisely and emotionally.

Conclusion

The purpose of this survey is to record the most interesting solutions for museum audio guide tours. Current technology provides plenty of computational power, connectivity, and imaging capabilities. Future needs will require mobile devices with more computational power.